

A Master Thesis Research:

Coopetition and the Dynamics of Ecosystem Strategy: A Study of Leading Firms in the Generative AI Landscape

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Abstract

This thesis explores how leading AI firms engage in cooptation to gain competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem. While cooptation is well-studied in mature industries, its strategies in nascent and evolving ecosystems remains underexplored.

The study employs a qualitative, inductive multi-case study approach grounded in Eisenhardt's theory-building method to analyze strategic interactions among incumbents (e.g., Microsoft, Google, Amazon) and newcomers (e.g., OpenAI, Anthropic, Perplexity, Deepseek, Qwen) from 2018 to 2025. Findings reveal three distinct cooptation strategies: strategic bilateral alliances to access resources, open-model collaboration to promote adoption, and platform-based model aggregation to strengthen ecosystem control.

Newcomers rely on cooptation for resources and legitimacy, while incumbents leverage it to hedge uncertainty and set ecosystem standards. The study concludes that cooptation is not only a mechanism to drive innovation, but also a tool for ecosystem orchestration and strategic positioning.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, generative AI has been one of the most disruptive and transformative innovations. Generative AI is changing how firms create value, compete and innovate. These technologies are not only tools to improve efficiency, they are also platforms that integrate AI into search engines, infrastructures and digital products. As technology advanced over the years and several new capabilities were introduced, the competitive era in Generative AI shifted dramatically. Firms who were once rivals, began to cooperate in developing models and setting industry standards. In this rapidly evolving ecosystem, cooptation, meaning simultaneous act of cooperation and competition, becomes crucial for firms to strategize in order to win the competition.

This study joins two main academic conversations: First, the literature on cooptation strategy which explores how firms collaborate with competitors to access resources, manage interdependencies, and drive innovation under conditions of uncertainty (Gnyawali & Park, 2011; Hoffmann et al., 2018). Second, to the studies on digital ecosystems and platform strategies, which explores how firms orchestrate platforms, strategize, and compete through infrastructure and modular innovation (Jacobides et al., 2018; Eisenmann et al., 2011; Adner, 2017). From the literature on cooptation, this study explores the idea that competitive advantage can be built upon these cooptation partnerships, while they might seem paradoxical and risky. Regarding ecosystem literature, It utilizes concepts such as platform envelopment and ecosystem architecture to analyze how firms leverage cooptation to co-design the broad ecosystem.

There has been a growing interest in how firms form cooptation alliances or partnerships to compete in digital and nascent ecosystems. Researchers have explored cooptation in often mature sectors such as pharmaceuticals and automotive, while focusing on how they develop products jointly or how they exchange resources while having tensions (Bouncken et al., 2017; Tidström, 2013). Researchers studying on platform ecosystems have explored how digital

platforms enable modular contributions, complementor engagement, and governance shaping (Gawer & Cusumano, 2002; Jacobides et al., 2018).

However, existing research has primarily focused on coopetition in mature industries, while there is limited attention towards nascent platform ecosystems such as generative AI. Furthermore, fewer studies have compared how incumbents and newcomers engage in coopetition differently based on factors such as resource position. This gap is problematic because without an understanding of how coopetition is utilized in such ecosystems, we may overlook its role as a tool for shaping ecosystems, a hedging strategy and a mechanism to determine the future trajectory of the industry.

To address this research question: How do leading AI companies engage in coopetition to build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem? This study uses a qualitative, multi-case approach to explore strategic partnerships among leading AI firms from 2018 to 2025. The research includes both incumbents (e.g., Microsoft, Google, Meta, Amazon) and newcomers (e.g., OpenAI, Anthropic, Perplexity, DeepSeek) allowing a comparative analysis across various strategic logics.

Through this research, I intend to make these primary contributions. First, I contribute to coopetition theories by how firms leverage coopetition in nascent and rapidly evolving ecosystems. Second, I extend the research on platform ecosystem strategy by highlighting that coopetition is not only a mechanism for joint innovation, but also a tool for shaping the ecosystem. Third, I offer a study in the timeframe (2018-2025) in order to highlight how different types of firms (newcomers and incumbents) navigate interdependence and technological uncertainty via various rationales.

2. Literature review

In exploring how firms build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem, it is necessary to analyze the strategic rationale behind coopetition. Coopetition is defined as “the simultaneous presence of competition and cooperation among firms” (Gnyawali & Charleton, 2018), which acts as a catalyst for innovation in high technology industries. Coopetition “enables firms to pursue advanced technological development and disruptive innovations” but requires carefully balancing joint and private gains (Gnyawali & Charleton, 2018). This balance is critical in industries such as generative AI, where firms rely heavily on proprietary data and intellectual properties and talent expertise.

The research on strategic alliances presents a suitable foundation to understand these inter-firm interactions. Strategic alliances are defined as “voluntary arrangements between firms involving exchange, sharing, or co-development of products, technologies, or services” (Gulati, 1998). Traditional research on alliances focused on bilateral interactions to access resources, but in newer studies, it evolved into a more complex and multi-partner interaction (Lavie et al., 2012). Specifically, from a platform ecosystem point of view, these partnerships serve not merely value creation, but also shaping industry architectures. This shows newer trends in platformization, where firms transition from pipeline models to ecosystems of interdependent actors (Jacobides et al., 2018). This ecosystem perspective changes how firms design a competitive strategy. Firms in software ecosystems adopt complementary strategies meaning collaborating on shared infrastructure while competing in higher-margin verticals (Arora & Bokhari, 2007). In such contexts (digital ecosystems) coopetition drives both incremental and radical innovation, dependent on the governance mechanisms that regulate knowledge sharing, trust, and opportunism (Bouncken et al., 2015).

Managing competitions is critical. While some firms use open-sourcing in the generative AI ecosystem to accelerate innovation, the industry is characterized as knowledge intensive and includes proprietary data pipelines. That being said, the impact of coopetition on innovation

outcomes rely heavily on absorptive capacity and the appropriability regime (Ritala & Hurmelinna-Laukkanen, 2013). Coopetition in knowledge intensive industries can be a double-edged sword meaning that it could advance innovation but also risks exposing firms to leakage and competitive erosion (Bouncken & Kraus, 2013). Hoffmann et al. (2018) argues that cooperation is essential for system-level gains, yet individual firms must simultaneously protect their proprietary advantages. Managing power relations is necessary to avoid value capture imbalances (Williamson & De Meyer, 2012). In generative AI, distribution networks, talents and compute power are often concentrated in a few firms which creates dependency risks for smaller players.

Hannah and Eisenhardt (2018) describe ecosystem bottlenecks as components whose improvement can unlock growth across the system. Firms compete to access these bottlenecks to win the long-term race. In these dynamic and coopetitive ecosystems, the role of the ecosystem orchestrator becomes vital. Daymond et al. (2022) argue that ecosystem architects must manage emergence and evolution through inclusive yet boundary-setting strategies. In generative AI, firms such as Microsoft integrated competitors models into its own platform (e.g OpenAI models into Github).

Similarly, Khanagha et al. (2020) show how mutualism, cooperative value creation between firms, can support the emergence of new platform spaces. This is relevant to the case of generative AI since firms cooperate in order to co-develop a new frontier (e.g running on-device LLMs). This means collaborating on a shared new technology in order to compete on developer ecosystems or user interfaces. As uncertainty is high such as in the case of generative AI, strategy making becomes more complex. Furr and Eisenhardt (2021) argue that in such conditions, firms must integrate two approaches: leveraging existing capabilities (resource-based view) and engaging in real-time experimentation (strategy creation view). Coopetition enables firms to include both by accessing complementary resources while being flexible.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

This study explores how leading AI firms engage in cooptation to build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem. Since the GenAI industry is evolving rapidly and has a complex nature, a qualitative, inductive research design is used to capture the full dynamics of strategic interactions. Based on constructivist epistemology, the study takes a qualitative approach based on constructivism, which perceives reality as socially constructed by human agency (Creswell, 2007). In this case strategic narratives between firms show underlying processes of decision-making in a nascent ecosystem.

Based on a subjectivist ontology, the study imagines knowledge as value-laden, created out of the researcher's engagement with archival data (Levers, 2013). Business strategies are not only shaped by market conditions, but also by firm's resource positions, previous trajectories, and ecosystem constraints. Therefore, the study explores how these strategies emerge over a period of time. Since Socio-cultural mediation is the basis of knowledge (Levers, 2013), qualitative analysis is appropriate.

The research follows Eisenhardt's (1989) theory-building approach using multiple case studies, suitable for examining complex phenomena such as cooptation where the boundaries between players, alliances, and technologies are fluid. This methodology allows for cross-case comparison and pattern recognition while retaining the contextual depth of each case.

3.2 Context and Sample

The study targets leading tech firms leading GenAI R&D. Purposive sampling involves cases that meet criteria to determine relevance (Patton, 2002). Selection criteria were defined to ensure theoretical relevance and cross-case comparability:

- The firm is a leader in generative AI research and development.
- The firm has monetization strategies tied to GenAI (e.g., API licensing, cloud integration, subscription models).
- The company's AI strategy is publicly documented in reports, filings and press releases.

Firms meeting these criteria include Microsoft, Google, Meta, OpenAI, Anthropic, Amazon, and others. The final sample size is based on the richness and availability of archival data and the level of theoretical saturation, where new themes emerging no longer occur (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The sample balances the incumbents and newcomers to include structural asymmetries in competition.

3.3 Data Collection

The study relies on archival data to analyze the competition strategies in Generative AI. Data include:

- Corporate reports, investor calls, and earnings transcripts.
- Press releases and official blog posts
- Media interviews with executives and technical leaders.
- Regulatory filings (e.g., SEC reports for public firms).
- Industry and academic analyses of AI trends and ecosystems.

The time frame covers 2018 to 2025, to cover the period when first models were announced and strategic alliances in GenAI matured. Iterative data collection refines the dataset with each gain of insight (Corbin & Strauss, 2008) to ensure in-depth understanding of strategies and their adoption to market trends.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data analysis process followed a combination of grounded theory techniques with Eisenhardt's (1989) iterative case comparison method, which is well-suited for theory building from multi-case data. The process began within-case analysis, meaning each firm's strategies were analyzed to understand how these alliances were started and positioned among competitors. This step presented the contextual depth needed to understand the logic of cooperation behaviors.

Following this, the next step was the cross-case comparison, where the strategic narratives were put alongside each other to identify emerging patterns. This step provided insights on consistent cooperation mechanisms and the difference of strategies between incumbents and newcomers. This was crucial since it provided insights that were not visible in isolated cases for example the relational dynamics and competitive tensions.

Coding was done manually and iteratively. In the beginning phase, raw data from the cooperation timeline was extracted (e.g. cloud partnership, investments, etc) and were labeled through open coding to identify strategic actions. Then these codes were refined through axial coding and grouped related actions into broader conceptual categories. Later on, selective coding was used to integrate these categories into higher-order themes that captured the underlying strategic rationale of cooperation. Throughout this process, New events were continually evaluated in relation to existing codes and categories to do revisions where necessary and enable the gradual refinement of thematic structures.

3.4.1 Application of Eisenhardt's Case Study Method

Eisenhardt Step	Application in This Study
1. Getting Started	Defined a focused research question on how leading AI firms engage in coopetition to build competitive advantage. Identified key constructs such as coopetition and competitive advantage.
2. Selecting Cases	Selected leading AI firms (e.g., Microsoft, OpenAI, Anthropic, Amazon, Meta) to represent various ecosystem roles (incumbents vs newcomers)
3. Crafting Instruments and Protocols	Collected archival data from company reports, press releases, interviews, and regulatory filings. Developed a coopetition event timeline covering 2018–2025.
4. Entering the Field	Iterated between data collection and analysis. Updated the dataset as new events appeared (e.g investments)
5. Analyzing Data	Performed narrative reconstructions of each firm’s strategic interactions to understand coopetition patterns and compared strategies across firms.
6. Shaping Hypotheses	Used thematic coding (open, axial, and selective) to build higher-order categories and compare them with prior literature for theoretical alignment.
7. Enfolding Literature	Compared emerging patterns with existing theories on coopetition and platform ecosystems to refine and validate findings.
8. Reaching Closure	Achieved theoretical saturation as no new themes emerged after multiple iterations.

Table 1 : Data Analysis Steps

3.5 Validation

To ensure credibility of the findings, the study used data triangulation across archival sources, including corporate press releases, regulatory filings, executive interviews, and industry analyses (Flick, 2004). Strategic events were coded if they were mentioned in at least two sources. This reduced the risk of misinterpretation and enhanced reliability of the data. Moreover, the longitudinal scope of the dataset (2018–2025) enhanced credibility by identifying patterns in coopetition strategy over time.

Reliability was ensured through a structured audit trail which documented the whole research process, and described all the procedures undertaken, from the point of data collection to coding and theme construction, to provide transparency and replicability.

Transferability was supported by providing contextualized descriptions of the research context, including detailed explanations of firm selection criteria and ecosystem roles. These descriptions allow readers to evaluate the relevance of the findings beyond the generative AI context and apply them in other emerging technological ecosystems.

To ensure confirmability, the study used memo writing and peer debriefing to reduce researcher bias. Coding processes and emerging patterns were regularly reviewed and challenged to maintain consistency. These strategies align with Lincoln and Guba’s (1985) criteria for trustworthiness in qualitative research.

4. Findings

Date (Quarter)	Company A	Company B	Relationship Type	Short Description
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Q3 2018	Microsoft	Amazon	Cross-Platform Integration	Alexa–Cortana voice assistant integration for mutual functionality access.
Q3 2019	Microsoft	OpenAI	Strategic Partnership & Investment	\$1 billion Azure partnership for AI model deployment and joint research.
Q2 2020	Microsoft	OpenAI	Infrastructure Collaboration	Built AI supercomputer on Azure exclusively for OpenAI.
Q3 2020	Microsoft	OpenAI	Technology Licensing	Exclusive GPT-3 license granted to Microsoft.
Q1 2022	Perplexity AI	Microsoft	Infrastructure Access	Partnering with Microsoft’s Azure to gain scale and reliability.
Q3 2022	Meta	Microsoft, Google, Amazon	Open-Source Alliance	PyTorch Foundation launched with multiple Big Tech founding members.
Q4 2022	Google	Anthropic	Cloud & Investment Deal	\$300M investment, making Google Cloud the preferred provider for Anthropic.
Q1 2023	Microsoft	OpenAI	Expanded Strategic Alliance	Multi-billion-dollar partnership extension with Azure exclusivity.
Q2 2023	Amazon Microsoft Google	Hugging Face	Strategic Cloud Partnership	They partnered with the open-source community Hugging Face.
Q1 2023	Microsoft	OpenAI	Product Integration	Integration of OpenAI's GPT into Bing search engine.

Q3 2023	Meta	Microsoft	Joint Release & Cloud Partnership	Joint release of Llama 2 on Azure and Windows platforms.
Q3 2023	Meta	Amazon	Infrastructure & Model Sharing	Partnership to offer Llama 2 models on Amazon AWS.
Q3 2023	Amazon	Anthropic	Strategic Cloud Alliance & Investment	Up to \$4B investment and AWS cloud partnership.
Q3 2023	Anthropic	Google	Expanded Investment & Cloud Alliance	Google commits additional \$1.5B investment and deepens cloud ties.
Q3 2023	Anthropic	OpenAI, Google, Microsoft	Industry Alliance	Formation of the Frontier Model Forum to promote AI safety.
Q3 2023	Anthropic	Perplexity	Platform Integration	Integration of Claude 2 into Perplexity's AI platform.
Q4 2024	Amazon	Anthropic	Increased Investment & Exclusivity	Additional \$4B investment and primary training partner agreement.
Q1 2025	Anthropic	OpenAI, Google, DeepMind, Microsoft	Standards-Level Interoperability	Anthropic published the open Model Context Protocol (MCP); OpenAI, DeepMind and Microsoft all adopted MCP in their agent platforms to enable multi-agent interoperability.

Table 2 : Coopetition Timeline Table (2018-2025)

The analysis of the 2018-2025 timeline of generative AI shows several patterns of coopetition (simultaneous cooperation and competition) among new entrants (e.g. OpenAI, Anthropic, xAI, Perplexity, Deepseek, Qwen) and incumbents (e.g. Microsoft, Google, Meta, Amazon). These patterns are drawn from empirical data and strategies these companies utilized to navigate the

generative AI ecosystem. Three key themes emerged and I compared how newcomers versus incumbents adapted these cooperation strategies.

4.1 Theme 1: Bilateral Strategic Alliances for Market Positioning

One key pattern that emerges from the cooperation of leading AI firms in the Generative AI ecosystem is bilateral alliances. These leading tech firms have formed strategic partnerships to secure industry bottlenecks in order to enhance their market position. These alliances (e.g. Microsoft with OpenAI, Google with Anthropic, and Amazon with Anthropic) combine cooperation and competition (“cooperation”) to gain access to latest technological advancements. While these partnerships can provide the partners customer lock-in and competitive advantage, some industry observers and committees such as US Federal Trade Commission (FTC) announced concerns that these deals might stifle competition in the evolving AI ecosystem (Reuters, 2025).

Microsoft–OpenAI (2019–present): Microsoft’s partnership with OpenAI started in 2019 and grew over time. Microsoft invested \$1 billion in OpenAI to become the exclusive partner, developing AI technologies on Microsoft Azure (OpenAI, 2019). In January 2025, Microsoft announced that this partnership extends until 2030, showing continued access of Microsoft to OpenAI’s models and IP. Microsoft noted that OpenAI’s API would remain exclusive to Microsoft’s Azure and the revenue from these models is shared both ways to benefit both parties (Microsoft Corporate Blogs, 2025). This strategy was also aligned with Microsoft’s goal to integrate GPT models into its existing systems (e.g. Bing and Copilot). Microsoft’s president, Satya Nadella, stated that the partnership “has fostered more AI innovation and competition, while preserving independence for both companies” (CNBC, 2023). There have been some concerns regarding this partnership from FTC which states that Microsoft’s investment and exclusivity clauses would make the competition unfair, which Microsoft reacted by opting out of the board-observer seat at OpenAI to alleviate regulatory issues (Reuters, 2024). Microsoft’s rationale behind this strategy was locking-in OpenAI models and being the sole company to

commercialize OpenAI models on Azure. Also, Microsoft hedged its bets by improving internal AI efforts such as hiring AI teams and developing Copilot features simultaneously, ensuring that it is not only dependent on OpenAI (Technology Magazine, 2025). In sum, the Microsoft-OpenAI alliance is an example of a cooperative alliance where both parties align on R&D projects but each side acts independently to capture Generative AI market share.

However, there were some tensions in the Microsoft–OpenAI alliance recently, showing the double-edged sword nature of cooperative alliances. According to TechCrunch (2025), OpenAI executives considered accusing Microsoft of antitrust behavior and seeking federal regulatory review of their agreement. The reason was OpenAI's acquisition of the AI coding startup Windsurf (Reuters, 2025). OpenAI resisted Microsoft's access to Windsurf's intellectual property, being concerned that Microsoft can leverage this to improve its own AI coding platform GitHub Copilot. By accessing Windsurf's IP, Microsoft can vertically integrate across cloud and developer tools and gain dominance in this specific niche. These tensions show how asymmetric alliances and power imbalances can create strategic conflicts especially if it is about control over IPs.

Google–Anthropic (2023–present): Google has a partnership with Anthropic (the developer of the Claude models), an AI startup founded by ex-OpenAI employees in 2021 (Contrary Research, n.d.). In 2023, Google invested more than \$2 billion in Anthropic, followed by an additional \$1 billion in January 2025 to deepen the partnership (Reuters, 2025). Google's move can be seen as a hedge and an effort to compete in the Generative AI ecosystem. In this case, investing in Anthropic (OpenAI rival), was a strategic move to strengthen and improve AI offerings. As pointed out by analysts in Financial Times “Google created the technology that makes AI models like Anthropic's Claude possible. However, the company has struggled to commercialize its AI, making the Anthropic investment a way to help it compete with the likes of Amazon and Meta.” (PYMNTS, 2025).

Google's partnership with Anthropic is not strictly exclusive. This deal was under investigation over the concerns of anti-trust laws and unfair competition. In November 2024, The Competition

and Markets Authority (CMA) noted that the Google-Anthropic deal was cleared and Google “has not acquired material influence” over Anthropic and that Anthropic is free to use multiple cloud providers (Landi, 2024). By avoiding an exclusive partnership, Google gains access to Claude models and integrates them into its own products but leaves Anthropic free to partner with other cloud providers (e.g. AWS).

Amazon–Anthropic (2023–present): Amazon partnered with Anthropic mostly to expand its cloud offerings. In 2024, Amazon announced to double its investment in Anthropic to \$8 billion. Anthropic agreed to make AWS the primary cloud provider for mission-critical training workloads, Also they agreed to train Anthropic’s Claude models on AWS’s custom Trainium chips, indicating a deepened partnership (Anthropic, 2024). Amazon has plans to integrate Claude into Alexa plus, while formerly relying on Amazon’s own AI (Anthropic, 2025). Analysts saw Amazon's additional investments in Anthropic as a growth strategy for AWS. D.A. Davidson analyst Gil Luria noted that the investment was “essential for Amazon to stay in a leadership position in AI” (Reuters, 2024). Furthermore, Amazon can leverage Claude models to enhance Alexa assistant, therefore boost engagements and monetize this platform. While lacking in-house LLMs, Amazon turned to Anthropic to regain its competitive position in the Generative AI ecosystem.

In summary, These bilateral alliances show cooperation in Generative AI. Microsoft, Google and Amazon form alliances with tech startups, while competing in overlapping markets. These alliances often aim to lock-in cutting edge technologies. These partnerships can be seen as a hedging strategy for bigger firms, while an opportunity for startups to scale up and leverage cloud infrastructure capabilities. Cooperation via alliances became a crucial strategy, which firms cooperated intimately with one player in order to better compete with others. Each of these alliances created a mini-ecosystem (e.g. OpenAI-Microsoft, Anthropic-Google/Amazon) in order to compete in this landscape.

4.2 Theme 2: Open-Model Cooperation for Ecosystem Leverage

Another pattern is open collaboration with the broader AI community as a competing strategy. Some incumbents and newcomers gave up their proprietary control over their models and opened up their platforms in order to cooperate with researchers and developers to improve innovation and adoption and more importantly to compete against closed players. An example is Meta's open-source approach. In early 2023, Meta released LLaMA to academic researchers and later that year released LLaMA 2 for free commercial use in partnership with Microsoft (Meta AI, 2023; Meta, 2023). Meta positioned this as a "democratizing AI" move which allowed developers worldwide to build upon LLaMA 2 and even let Microsoft host it on Azure as the preferred partner. By taking this open approach, Meta cooperated with the AI developer ecosystem and Microsoft(a competitor) to make its model known. In contrast to OpenAI's closed API model, Meta released these open models to offer open alternatives to compete with OpenAI's closed model. This strategy aims to undermine proprietary model competitors such as OpenAI by promoting adoption and standardization of Meta's models. As more developers engage with open models like LLaMA, Meta positions itself to capture long-term developer value and gain ecosystem dominance.

The fact that Microsoft engaged in this open-source alliance despite being the OpenAI's investor shows how appealing the open strategy is and how necessary it is to adapt to an always changing paradigm. Alibaba had a similar tactic in China in 2023. It released AI models under open-source licenses to allow developers to use and modify them.(Reuters, 2025). This approach included collaborating with the AI community, even if it meant sharing models that competitors could use. This strategy might not be the direct example of cooperation between Alibaba (a Chinese company) and Western firms but shows how this open-source strategy can challenge closed approaches in the Generative AI ecosystem. The main aim was to boost its presence by widespread adoption. Alibaba creates competitive pressure by open-sourcing its models. Competitors must either adapt to Alibaba's widely used models or pay significant costs developing models themselves. Therefore, openness becomes a competitive leverage. Meta and Alibaba used open-sourcing as a form of cooperation both directly and indirectly meaning that they gave up some control, in order to compete with their rivals.

Another example of Newcomers with an open approach shocking the Generative AI ecosystem was the emergence of a player from China, called DeepSeek. In 2023, DeepSeek stunned the

industry by releasing an open weight LLM that challenged the best models by a fraction of the cost. DeepSeek's R1 model which was under an MIT open license performed benchmarks comparable to GPT models. It even caused NVIDIA's stock to drop since investors were afraid that this efficient model could reduce demand for NVIDIA's computing chips(BBC News, 2025). Similarly, Hugging face, a startup founded in 2016, became a neutral ground for tech giants to collaborate. In 2023, Hugging Face raised \$235 million from a collection of tech giants(Google, Amazon, NVIDIA, Intel, IBM, Salesforce, and others all invested together(Reuters, 2023). These firms which are normally rivals, showed interest in collaborating together in supporting the open-source AI community. This multi-competitor collaboration illustrates that despite each of them selling AI services individually, they collaborated jointly to support a community driven platform and to ensure that no single firm controls all key models.

Overall, this theme shows that AI players engage in competition whether by open-sourcing models or co-investing in community-driven platforms indicated a powerful strategy.

4.3 Theme 3: Platform Competition through Model Aggregation

A third pattern shows how incumbents and newcomers engaged in competition via model aggregation. Unlike theme 2, where companies gave up proprietary control, this theme is about firms selectively including rival's technologies into their own platforms to improve their competitiveness. These companies(mostly tech giants) cooperate with rivals by hosting and distributing their models to offer a broader range of choices to customers.

Platform provider bundles functionalities or products from rivals into its own offerings to block rival's access to users and harness network effects (Eisenmann et al., 2011). This framework is helpful in explaining this shift in competitive dynamic in the Generative AI ecosystem. By

aggregating rival models, they increase their ecosystem's dominance and attractiveness, therefore locking in users. This type of cooperation includes cooperating with a rival's model to attract users and customers, while competing on user acquisition and infrastructure.

One example would be Amazon's strategy for Amazon Bedrock. Launched in 2023, Bedrock not only includes Amazon's proprietary models (Titan, Alexa) but also hosted competitor models such as Anthropic (Claude), Stability AI (Stable Diffusion), and AI21 Labs (Amazon, 2023). These companies were all potential competitors for Amazon's own models but Amazon aimed to provide all-in-one cloud space. This cooperation helped Amazon to compete with Google Cloud and Microsoft's Azure not only through model performance but through ecosystem offerings. This indicates a shift from product-based competition towards a platform-centric approach.

Google had a similar approach, while focusing on in-house models such as Gemini and Bard Google increased its offerings by integrating Anthropic's Claude on Google Cloud (Google Cloud, 2024). A strategic decision to compete and remain relevant in a constantly changing ecosystem.

Newcomers also engaged in platform cooperation. The technical architecture of Perplexity AI, which competes with traditional search engines like Google and Bing, relies on Microsoft's Bing search index and OpenAI's language models (Perplexity, 2024). Perplexity utilized these models to develop a differentiated product which is a conversational search engine. By deploying this strategy, Perplexity used the incumbent's capabilities to compete and challenge the incumbents themselves.

In 2025, the Model Context Protocol (MCP) initiative illustrated a form of platform cooperation. Anthropic published MCP as an open protocol for AI-agent interoperability (Anthropic, 2024). OpenAI, Google and Microsoft used this for their platforms. While being fierce competitors, they agreed on a shared standard to improve cross-system compatibility. This suggests that, beyond racing on AI models, leading AI firms also collectively design the rules shaping the Generative AI ecosystem.

The establishment of the Frontier Model Forum in 2023 by OpenAI, Microsoft, Google, and Anthropic reflects a collaborative effort to ensure safety rules, transparency, and governance

standards.(Frontier Model Forum, n.d.). While being competitors, their collaboration through the Forum indicates a shared interest in providing ecosystem stability and maintaining public trust.

In summary, Theme 3 suggests a distinct cooptation logic. Platform owners(often tech giants) aggregating competitor's technologies or co-designing shared rules to enhance their own competitive advantage. Despite Theme 2 which was focused on open collaboration and innovation, Theme 3 was more around cooperating with rivals to improve market position. This strategy is more common among Cloud providers.

4.4 Newcomer vs. Incumbent Cooptation Strategies

Across these themes, a distinction emerges on how newcomers and incumbents leverage cooptation in the generative AI ecosystem. Newcomers often engage in cooptation to grow and gain legitimacy (Gupta et al., 2025). Forming partnerships with incumbents enable startups to access infrastructure,distribution channels and funding to scale up. Simultaneously, such alliances signal credibility and reduce the risk for investors to partner with the company.

In their early days, companies like OpenAI and Anthropic, formed bilateral alliances with Microsoft and Google (Theme 1), giving a stake of the company in exchange for funding and market credibility. Startups like Deepseek and Qwen, challenged the entire ecosystem by releasing open-source models. (Theme 2), engaging the AI community to refine their models. On platforms (Theme 3) newcomers rely heavily on the incumbent's API and infrastructure evident in the example of Perplexity AI, being a wrap-around OpenAI's GPT model and Bing's search index. In all instances, cooptation seem a necessity for resource-limited newcomers to compete against tech giants.

In contrast, incumbents utilize cooptation as a hedging strategy and a means to set ecosystem governance rules. Microsoft's exclusive partnership with OpenAI was followed by a complementary hedging strategy which was hosting Meta's LLaMA 2 on Azure (Themes 1 & 2)

to ensure having both proprietary and community-driven AI innovations. Google's minority stake in Anthropic served the same purpose. It allowed Google to hedge its bets while remaining agile in an industry that can pivot overnight (Brooks, 2025). Incumbents also joined coalitions(Theme 3) such as Frontier Forums Model and Hugging Face platform to set industry standards and maintain a balanced industry structure. In sum, the incumbent's coopetition is shaped by where they could expand their influence and hedge against uncertainty or to set ecosystem norms.

5. Discussion

This study set out to examine how leading AI companies engage in coopetition to build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem. Based on an empirical analysis of alliances and strategic moves from 2018 to 2025, the Findings reveal three themes and forms of coopetition among leading AI companies in generative AI ecosystem: bilateral strategic alliances, open-model collaboration, and platform-based model aggregation. These types of coopetition alliances illustrate how companies simultaneously compete and cooperate in order to advance innovation, gain market share, and shape the ecosystem. Not only these findings resonate with existing theory that views coopetition as a way of joint value creation and gaining competitive advantage (Hoffmann et al., 2018), but also extends current theory by illustrating that how coopetition in an nascent industry and ecosystem like Generative AI is not only a vital strategy but also a mechanism for setting standards and platform dominance.

5.1 Bilateral Strategic Alliances for Market Positioning

Incumbent firms form alliances with startups to secure AI advancements. Such alliances enable firms to access assets from the partner e.g. infrastructure, data or talent, while jointly developing AI advancements. In practice, big and small firms in the Generative AI ecosystem enter these partnerships to acquire strategic resources, reduce costs, and enhance reputation (Gupta et al., 2025). By aligning their resources together, partners can capture ecosystem “bottlenecks”. These types of alliances are aimed at these crucial points by investing in next generating models to win the long-term AI race. This study extends existing cooptition theory by showing that, in nascent ecosystems, bilateral alliances are often used not only to access resources, but to strategically preempt competitors and block the access of other rivals to critical technological bottlenecks. Bottlenecks are crucial since actors can control them to shape value flows and influence the entire ecosystem’s trajectory (Hannah & Eisenhardt, 2018).

At the same time, these alliances include the classic cooptition paradox and tension. While cooptition can bring various benefits e.g. encourage innovation and R&D, it also generates tensions. Trade-offs between competition and cooperation can be transformed and managed, but not eliminated (Hoffmann et al., 2018). High competitive intensity can substantially diminish collaborative value in cooptition alliances and encourage firms to guard their proprietary knowledge more closely and prioritize private gains (Bouncken et al., 2020).

5.2 Open-Model Cooptition for Ecosystem Leverage

A second prominent theme of cooptition in the generative AI ecosystem is open-model collaboration which includes a strategic move by companies to release open-weight AI models (e.g. Meta’s LLaMA) and encourage contributions of broad ecosystem players. This type of openness invites developers and researchers to build upon existing core models and turn potential competitors into collaborators. The modular architecture of generative AI models makes this strategy feasible by integrating complementary pieces into a shared technological

platform without requiring centralized innovation and coordination (Jacobides et al., 2018). By engaging various players, open-model competition promotes adoption, advances innovation, improves ecosystem dominance.

This study advances existing theory by suggesting that openness is not only a collaborative effort but a competitive leverage. It is a form of ecosystem shaping which cooperation is utilized to increase user lock-in around a company's own infrastructure and APIs. Specifically this strategy is aimed at closed architecture firms that rely heavily on their proprietary API models (e.g. OpenAI's ChatGPT) to weaken their market dominance.

However, this strategy brings tensions. Excessive openness might diminish competitive advantage by letting rivals appropriate innovations. Without sufficient control over complementary assets such as data, compute or distribution channels, firms risk not capturing value that they created, thus appropriated by rivals (Broekhuizen et al., 2021). Furthermore, poor control over model quality in these open platforms may lead to harming user experience and trust (Gawer & Cusumano, 2002). Therefore, firms must always look for balance between openness for maximum adoption and sufficient control for value appropriation.

5.3 Platform Competition through Model Aggregation

The third pattern is platform-based competition, cloud providers such as AWS, Azure and Google Cloud aggregate multiple AI models in their cloud to offer customers in a single space. This bundling approach is explicit in the concept of “platform envelopment”. Platform envelopment is bundling one’s own functionality with a target’s to capture network effects (Eisenmann et al., 2011) . In the Generative AI ecosystem, this means that cloud providers host their competitors' products in order to make their own platform more attractive and lock in customers. What is distinct in the generative AI ecosystem is that model aggregation is not merely a tactic to enhance the proposed value but is also a preemptive strategic move on how innovation is distributed and circulates in the ecosystem. Cloud providers gain access to developer workflows,

rivals' user base, even when the model offered is not their own. Thus, these platforms (often incumbents) benefit from the rival's innovation and competition on model innovation and performance. This strategy goes beyond traditional bundling aimed at adding value to the platform (Eisenmann et al., 2011). It's more about locking-in competitors within the infrastructure and retaining dominance. A cooperation aimed at winning the cloud race.

Ecosystem architects can deliberately invite competing offerings to enhance the platform's value (Daymond et al., 2023). Cooperation happens by hosting other's models which increases platform's utility and network scale but yet competition is on model's performance and ease of use. This leads to intense network effects and makes the platform more valuable when each model is added and more developers use the platform. Platforms gain value and influence as additional complementors join, due to indirect network effects that increase utility for all sides of the market (Eisenmann et al., 2011). Moreover, leading AI firms also engage in setting standards and governance through open consortias e.g Frontier Model Forum to stabilize the ecosystem.

These findings extend existing theories of platform cooperation by arguing that in evolving ecosystems such as generative AI, aggregation serves two purposes, while it increases platform attractiveness, it also can be seen as a defensive tactic to absorb rival's threats. In this way, incumbents turn openness and aggregation into a governance mechanism that controls innovation circulation in the ecosystem.

5.4 Incumbents vs. Newcomers in Cooperation

To look at it from a different angle, this study also revealed how cooperation tactics are deferred between incumbents and newcomers in the generative AI ecosystem. While prior research has explored resource alliances or hedging in general, this study highlights how these strategies are specific in the context of Generative AI, where newcomers are dependent on incumbent's infrastructures and platform access and model adoption are intertwined with the firm's competitive position.

For Newcomers, often startups or small firms, cooptation acts as a necessity rather than a choice. Since these firms often lack capital and distribution channels, these companies enter alliances with incumbents to access critical resources. This strategy reflects the resource dependence logic which firms depend on external resources controlled by others, driving them to form alliances to secure critical resources and reduce uncertainty and dependency (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). In generative AI context, these dependencies may not be purely financial, it also involves access to fine-tuning pipelines and developer ecosystem and talents. While these cooptation alliances present growth opportunities for newcomers, it often leaves startups vulnerable to power imbalances, data control issues, and dependency on large firms (Gupta et al., 2025).

In contrast, incumbents already with intensive infrastructure capabilities and brand reputation, engage in cooptation towards a different goal. These firms leverage cooptation alliances as strategic hedges in order to reduce uncertainty in a rapidly evolving industry. Based on Real options logic, which suggests firms form alliances or make investments not as irreversible commitments, but as flexible options that allow for future action depending on how uncertainty resolves (Trigeorgis & Reuer, 2017). This study extends this logic by highlighting that incumbents selectively partner with competitors or disruptors to externalize innovation, including emerging state-of-the-art models, while having the flexibility to withdraw. Therefore, this strategy is not all about flexibility, It is a way to stay embedded in the evolution of the ecosystem.

6. Conclusion

6.1 Summary of Key Findings

This thesis analyzed how leading AI companies engage in cooptation to build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem. Using empirical evidence from 2018 to 2025, the study identified three emerging patterns : (1) bilateral strategic alliances, where firms form alliances to co-develop cutting edge technologies while competing in downstream markets; (2)

open-model coopetition, where players release open models or con-invest in open platforms for promote widespread adoption; and (3) platform coopetition, where firms(incumbents) aggregate rival's models or collectively shape industry standards.

Moreover, the study highlights that newcomers engage in coopetition alliances to gain legitimacy, resources, and distribution. However, incumbents leverage coopetition as a hedging strategy and as a means to shape ecosystem architectures and design. It illustrates how firms simultaneously compete and cooperate to navigate technological uncertainty and capture industry bottlenecks in a nascent yet rapidly evolving ecosystem.

6.2 Limitations

This study presents new insights on how leading AI companies engage in coopetition to build competitive advantage in the generative AI ecosystem, but several limitations must be noted. First, the study focuses on leading and dominant firms in this industry, therefore, the strategies among smaller firms and their tactics and logic might differ significantly. These smaller firms could be niche model developers or academic labs.

Second, the study is mainly based on publicly available data on partnerships such as press releases and firm's announcements. This limits the study to gain deeper insights on the logic behind strategic decisions or more importantly the long-term impact of these alliances. coopetition nuances including internal tensions or cultural differences between companies remain outside the scope of this study.

Third, the generative AI landscape is quite dynamic with new technologies and market entrants showing up rapidly. Therefore, the themes and patterns might present only a snapshot of the playing field dynamics. Upcoming advancements such as AI edge or AGI might significantly change the usage of coopetition. This limitation invites scholars to work on longitudinal approaches and comparative studies that can track how coopetition strategies evolve in response to ecosystem maturation and technological disruption.

6.3 Implications and Future Research

This study contributes to existing theory by applying competition and nascent ecosystem frameworks to the generative AI landscape. It shows that traditional theories such as Resource Dependence Theory, platform envelopment and modular openness are relevant but also suggest new nuances. Practically, this serves as a study to better understand how and why these AI firms engage in coopetition and what might the challenges be.

Future research can explore this topic quantitatively. For example, scholars can measure how various coopetition tactics and strategies might affect innovation or market dominance. Comparing coopetition across different industries could reveal if these patterns are unique to a certain field. Additionally, studying how policy makers (antitrust bodies) might interact with coopetition alliances formed may help understand and provide valuable insights on how firms can navigate these nascent ecosystems.

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